

THE INFLUENCE OF SERVICE QUALITY OF PUBLIC LIBRARIES ON THE LIBRARY USER'S ENGAGEMENT

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The Influence of Service Quality of Public Libraries on the Library User's Engagement

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Abstract

In libraries, perceptions of high services quality to their target clients are typically able to draw out high level of satisfaction and engagement. Using the descriptive-regression research design, the study was conducted to determine the influence of service quality of public libraries on library user's engagement. It was performed using a survey questionnaire that was tested using Cronbach Alpha and Content Validity. Data were collected from 175 randomly selected respondents who are frequent professional library users in public libraries in Region XII, consisting of graduate students, businessmen and women, retired personnel, and those users who have pursued their law, master's, or doctor's degrees. The data were analyzed using simple linear regression analysis. Results from the quantitative analysis revealed that service quality of public libraries can significantly influence library user's engagement. Thus, it can be claimed that one effective way of enticing more individuals to use public libraries is to improve the level of service quality of public libraries. Based on the findings, it is strongly recommended that public library administrators provide public librarians with comprehensive and continuous professional development opportunities, including seminars, trainings, enrolling in library professional courses, and benchmarking effective strategies that build the confidence and competence of public librarians to improve the quality of services offered to library patrons.

Keywords: *library and information science, library skills, work performance, quantitative, Philippines*

Introduction

Libraries that provide high-quality services to their target customers are typically able to demonstrate high levels of user engagement. High user engagement reflects that the library meets patrons' needs. To further boost engagement, libraries must build strong customer relationships through quality services, competitive staff, and comprehensive collections. Numerous studies around the world have demonstrated that service quality significantly influences user engagement in public libraries. Mahmouda, Samanoudya, and Jung (2023) found that Dubai public libraries should consider the diverse needs of users to ensure engagement. Jasmine (2019) noted recent advancements in Dubai Municipality public libraries that have increased user engagement through improved service quality. What's On (2020) emphasized that public libraries should continue delivering high-quality services to meet user needs and boost engagement. Similarly, a service quality analysis of South Australia's Community Libraries by Murray, Cleland, and Townson (2020) revealed high user satisfaction and engagement due to exceeding user expectations.

In Asia, empirical evidence shows that service quality significantly influences library user engagement. Shafawi and Hassan (2018) found that higher service quality in Malaysian libraries increased user awareness and engagement. Gong and Yi (2018) demonstrated that service quality positively impacts user engagement in Japan, South Korea, China, Hong Kong, and Singapore. Nur and Fritantus (2021) reported that quality library services in Indonesia's North and Central Timor Regency border areas enhance user satisfaction and engagement. However, the West Sumatra Public Library in Indonesia did not meet customer expectations, leading to dissatisfaction and low engagement (Fithri, Adnan, & Syahmer, 2018).

In Bangladesh, studies by Alam (2021) and Hossain (2016) confirmed the positive effect of service quality on user engagement. Bhatti, Marwat, and Khan (2015) found that high-quality services at the Bahawalpur Central Public Library in Pakistan led to positive user perceptions and engagement. Noh and Chang (2020) showed that meeting user needs with adequate facilities, relevant collections, and qualified staff in South Korean public libraries significantly boosts user satisfaction and engagement.

In the Philippines, studies also indicate that service quality affects user engagement. Zalatar (2017) found that user engagement can be predicted by service quality dimensions like assurance, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, and tangibles. Alusen and Tiu (2019) revealed that the Multimedia Library in Lyceum of the Philippines, Laguna, needs improvements in individual attention, understanding specific needs, and delivering users' information needs for better empathy. For tangibility, updating books and improving facilities is necessary. Reliability requires accurate book segmentation, while assurance and responsiveness need trustworthy personnel to address problems effectively. Empathy can be enhanced through customer service training.

Aspa, Estacio, and Gabriel (2022) found that consistent quality service at the University of Baguio leads to increased user engagement by satisfying stakeholders. In the local context, observations and informal discussions with public librarians in North Cotabato reveal varying levels of service quality among public libraries. Some libraries excel in resource utilization, facilities, and services, with sufficient staff to meet user needs. However, others suffer from inadequate resources, poor facilities, and insufficient staff, resulting in low service quality. These disparities have prompted the researcher to analyze the relationship between service quality and user engagement. The study aims to provide empirical evidence to help public libraries and local governments develop plans to improve service quality and increase user engagement.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the influence of service quality of public libraries on library users' engagement in public libraries in Region XII. Particularly, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of service quality in public libraries in Region XII in terms of:
 - 1.1 assurance;
 - 1.2 empathy;
 - 1.3 reliability;
 - 1.4 responsiveness; and
 - 1.5 tangibility?
2. What is the level of user's engagement in public libraries in Region 12 in terms of:
 - 2.1 behavioral domain;
 - 2.2 emotional domain; and
 - 2.3 cognitive domain?
3. Can the service quality of public libraries influence library user engagement?

Literature Review

This section contains extensively studied and validated facts about service quality, user's engagement, and the influence of service quality on the library user's engagement.

Service Quality

Service quality refers to users' overall evaluation of a service. In libraries, it enables the provision of higher quality services. Sharabati and Abusaimh (2019) state that service quality is the difference between customer expectations and the actual service provided. Danish (2018) defines it as a comparison function related to customer expectations of the service. Fida et al. (2020) assert that service quality is the fundamental ability of a library to meet customer expectations. Elvira and Shpetim (2016) emphasize that service quality is a type of assessment representing a long-term evaluation.

To better visualize and analyze the services provided to our users. Parasuraman et al. (1988) developed a model for measuring service quality. These five service dimensions or criteria are used by users to evaluate the quality of a service. Moreover, Tabuyo et al. (2018) assessed quality of service using five dimensions such as assurance, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, and tangibility.

Assurance. Assurance in service quality pertains to highly skilled library staff who can earn users' trust. It involves the knowledge, courtesy, and ability of library staff to instill confidence and a sense of security during interactions (Setonio & Hidayat, 2022). Reddy (2017) notes that assurance measures how well library staff build trust through their expertise, skills, and behavior. Effective librarians, as emphasized by Phua et al. (2018), possess the knowledge, experience, and motivation to enhance library services while treating users with respect and kindness. Emiri & Olise (2022) highlight the importance of assurance in providing library and information services, where confident staff build strong relationships with users. Therefore, assurance ensures that library staff are knowledgeable, courteous, and trustworthy, creating a safe and comfortable environment where users feel encouraged to ask questions and access resources (Nur & Fritantus, 2021).

Empathy. Empathy in service quality within libraries refers to how well the library demonstrates care for its users, provides personalized attention, and makes them feel valued and special. High-quality personalized attention encourages patrons to return to the library. Reddy (2017) quantifies a library's ability to show compassion and consideration using an empathy scale. Library staff who are friendly, approachable, and responsive to user inquiries contribute significantly to fostering a sense of connection and belonging. Developing empathic skills among librarians is crucial, as it enhances communication and understanding of each user's needs, including those with special requirements (Bodaghi et al., 2016). Setonio & Hidayat (2022) emphasize that empathy involves providing individual attention, treating customers with care, and prioritizing their interests and needs. Therefore, empathy is essential for public library staff to effectively understand community needs, build relationships, facilitate good communication, provide personal attention, and meet the diverse needs of library users (Nur & Fritantus, 2021).

Reliability. Reliability in service quality refers to how well a library delivers on its promises regarding service, quality, and accuracy as established with patrons (Reddy, 2017). It encompasses the library's credibility and its ability to provide promised services and resources fully (Yu & Huang, 2020). Xu and Du (2018) emphasize the importance of reliability because users seek assurance that their library will reliably meet their specified requirements. Research indicates that reliability influences user satisfaction and engagement (Choshaly & Mirabolghasemi, 2019). Reliability involves the knowledge, courtesy, and ability of library personnel to inspire self-confidence, ensuring that services are provided correctly and timely, and that documents are stored without errors (Setonio & Hidayat, 2022). It also means offering immediate, accurate, and satisfying services, allowing users quick access to collections and services. Additionally, library staff must understand their duties and responsibilities to provide the highest quality service to users (Nur & Fritantus, 2021).

Responsiveness. Responsiveness in service quality refers to a library's commitment to assisting patrons by providing prompt and high-quality service. Users feel valued when they receive the best possible service, reflecting the library staff's willingness and ability to deliver quality service (Reddy, 2017). Responsiveness can be measured by how quickly staff respond to patrons' requests and how seriously they address their needs. Users are more satisfied when librarians promptly meet their needs (Jabeen et al., 2017). This dimension of service quality involves the service provider's willingness to help customers and provide timely services. Key attributes include informing customers about service delivery times, offering prompt assistance, and being ready to respond to customer requests (Setonio & Hidayat, 2022). Moreover, responsiveness is demonstrated by library staff's confidence in assisting users, being responsible, caring, and proactive in addressing complaints (Nur & Fritantus, 2021).

Tangibility. The tangibility aspect of service quality pertains to the physical appearance of the library environment, facilities, equipment, resources, staff, and media. Tangibility creates an immediate impression, and libraries need to leave users with a unique, memorable, and positive first impression to encourage future visits (Reddy, 2017). The ability to provide quality services is directly linked to the availability of physical resources like buildings and equipment (Emiri & Olise, 2022). Tangibility encompasses the appearance of facilities, equipment, and staff (Setonio & Hidayat, 2022). For example, the public library in North Central Timor Regency Library and Archives Service shows good tangibility through its well-maintained indoor and outdoor areas, available parking, and annual improvements in books, reading materials, facilities, and infrastructure. This positive appearance has led to an increase in users who feel proud to visit the library (Nur & Fritantus, 2021). Therefore, tangibility is crucial in delivering library services, as it helps develop a strong, positive, and inspiring user experience.

Library User Engagement

Library user engagement refers to the extent to which individuals interact with and utilize library resources, services, and activities. This includes borrowing materials, using digital resources, participating in events, seeking help from library staff, and engaging with other library offerings. High levels of user engagement suggest that the library is successfully meeting the needs and interests of its users.

To analyze and understand better the library engagement of public library users, here are the following literatures that support the library users' engagement when it comes to behavioral, emotional and cognitive domains. The following library user's engagement indicators are used by the users to evaluate their library engagement.

Behavioral Domain. Behavioral engagement refers to a user's observable actions or behavior with the libraries on its facilities, resources and services. There are different behavioral techniques, namely, counting updates, objective setting, social rewards, user's engagement exercises, and work environment variables, which can altogether upgrade library client engagement. Within the library setting, it is anticipated that the appropriation of these behavioral exercises will upgrade the behavioral engagement of library clients. Alzahrani, Mahmud, Ramayah, Alfarraj and Alalwan (2019) stated that the quality of library services has impact on behavioral intention and in actual utilization. Service quality has solid positive relationship to the degree of client fulfillment, and engagement with solid impact on behavioral viewpoint to utilize the library. Therefore, library user's engagement in terms of behavioral aspect has a positive and statistically significant effect on actual library use. It is significant in providing libraries holistic overview for harnessing the use of library resources and services in meeting users' ever-changing needs to increase users' awareness and enhance users' engagement of library services (Shafawi & Hassan, 2018).

Emotional Domain. Emotional engagement refers to the user's feelings or affective reactions towards the library facilities, resources or services. Joo, Choi and Baek (2018) observed that libraries with updated resources, adequate facilities and available services emotionally inspire users to engage more in libraries. And most practical strategies for public libraries to market their resources and services with effectively use of social media to better facilitate user engagement (Peacemaker, and Heinze, 2015). User engagement with emotional factors influences decisions and requires librarians to understand and create deeper relationship with library users to create more engagement. Additionally, emotional changes due to the mobile library's service interface, service functions and service environment were measured and found that the mobile service of the library has good usability (Zhao, Cao and Yang, 2020).

Cognitive Domain. Cognitive engagement pertains to a user's level of involvement in the decision-making process, including the effort expended to understand and evaluate the resources or service in libraries. Statistical analyses indicated that the level of user engagement with the OPAC (Online Public Access Catalog) of library was relatively low and perceived usability was only at a moderate level. Other findings suggested that cognitive absorption and computer self-efficacy significantly influenced the level of user engagement. Higher levels with increased user engagement on the use of library's OPAC. It was revealed that cognitive absorption, and basic computer skills had the most significant impact, on user engagement (Khosravi, Behzadi and Nowkarizi, 2024). Also, cognitive mapping is an innovative approach to explore user experience on mobile library services, on how users interact with mobile technology and their experience using the mobile library service (Fu & Inskip, 2019).

Influence of Service Quality on Library User's Engagement

Libraries that provide high-quality services to their target clients typically demonstrate high levels of user engagement, with service quality aspects significantly influencing this engagement (Quach et al., 2016). Libraries are seeking innovative ways to communicate and interact with users through their resources and services. The impact of these efforts varies by community and depends on the

resources and services utilized by clients (Kandampully et al., 2015). Low budgets can reduce the quality of service and user engagement. Jasmine (2019) noted that Dubai Municipality public libraries have recently made significant advancements by enhancing service quality, thereby increasing user engagement. Partap (2019) concluded that service quality, defined by the provision of good resources and library services, leads to higher user engagement. In a city library in Zambia, South Africa, high user engagement was observed in library access, facilities, and service quality, each significantly influencing overall user satisfaction and engagement (Nzazi, 2018).

In libraries, high perceptions of service quality lead to increased customer satisfaction and user engagement (Giovanis et al., 2016). Service quality in this context refers to the overall excellence of library facilities, resources, and services that meet users' expectations (Baada et al., 2019). Alam (2020) demonstrated that specific equipment and the responsiveness of library staff significantly impact user engagement. Twum et al. (2020) also found that all dimensions of service quality are positively correlated with library user engagement. Similarly, Moses et al. (2016) concluded that service quality has a significant positive impact on library user engagement. Recent research highlights that perceived service quality, including the delivery of relevant resources, positively influences user satisfaction and engagement (Uzir et al., 2021). Moreover, Farooq et al. (2019) studied Malaysian university libraries and found that service quality, assessed through dimensions like assurance, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, and tangibility, significantly influences user engagement. These studies collectively underscore the critical role of service quality in enhancing user satisfaction and engagement within library settings.

Further, public libraries globally are actively engaging their communities by transforming and enhancing service quality to better meet user needs (Munsanje & Hagwelele, 2018). In the United Arab Emirates, public libraries have innovatively expanded access to information, improved library collections, and optimized services, programs, and activities to foster greater library engagement (Zimba, Mavodza & Eid, 2015). Similarly, in Ghana, West Africa, public libraries are focusing on providing appropriate resources to enhance service quality and increase user engagement (United Nations, 2015). Measuring service quality in public libraries often involves assessing five dimensions: reliability, responsiveness, tangibility, assurance, and empathy. Studies indicate that higher user satisfaction with library services and resources correlates positively with increased engagement (Bhatnagar & Kumar, 2017). Moses et al. (2016) concluded from their study in Nigerian public libraries that service quality significantly influences both user engagement and satisfaction. These findings underscore the importance of quality service provision in public libraries worldwide to enhance user experiences and community engagement.

Public libraries in the 21st century is increasingly focused on delivering high-quality services to their patrons, recognizing that service quality significantly impacts user engagement. Previous studies highlight that service quality in public libraries is influenced by users' perceptions and expectations. When libraries effectively meet user needs through qualified staff, updated resources, and quality services, it tends to increase user engagement. Conversely, poor service quality can lead to dissatisfaction and reduced engagement among users. Studies also emphasize that user satisfaction with the expected quality of service correlates with increased utilization of library resources and services. Users who receive adequate help and support from library staff are more likely to engage actively with library offerings. Additionally, existing research often examines library service quality in terms of user satisfaction and loyalty. In the context of the Philippines, there is a growing recognition of the importance of service quality as a measure for assessing libraries. Further exploration of this topic is warranted, particularly to understand how enhancing service quality can lead to greater user engagement in Philippine libraries.

Methodology

This section presents the various processes and procedures employed in order to generate the data needed in this study. It includes the discussion of the research design, respondents, instruments of the study that were applied in order to interpret the data, procedure, and the ethical considerations, and data analysis used in order to analyze and interpret the data.

Research Design

This study employed descriptive-regression research design. The descriptive-regression research design was employed to determine if service quality provided by public libraries influenced user engagement. According to Nworgu (2015), a descriptive design aims at collecting data and describing data in a systematic manner such as the characteristics, features, or facts about a given population. This design was considered appropriate for the study because it would collect data and describe them in a systematic manner, specifically the level of service quality and users' engagement among public libraries in Region XII. In addition, Gravetter and Forzano (2018) claimed that the use of descriptive research involves measuring a variable as they exist naturally. Meanwhile, regression research is appropriate to use if the researcher wants to determine whether an independent variable can influence or predict a dependent variable (Kumari & Yadab, 2018). In the context of the study, this research design was employed because the researcher would like to determine if service quality provided by public libraries can influence library users' engagement among public libraries in Region XII.

Participants

The respondents of this study consisted of 175 respondents that were known to be frequent users of public libraries in Region XII, namely: Public Library A, Public Library B, Public Library C, Public Library D, and Public Library E. They were selected based on

the following inclusion and exclusion criteria. The criteria for the inclusion of respondents are the following: (1) those considered as frequent professional library users of the public library. These frequent library users are clients who visited and utilized library facilities, resources and most especially availed library services; (2) must be professional users such as graduate students, business men/women, retired personnel and those users who proceed their law, masters and doctors' degree; (3) must be professionals because they have already knowledge on different studies like conducting survey. They also have knowledge on how to evaluate the public libraries and most importantly they can clearly read and understand every statement presented on the survey questionnaire; (4) must visit the library with at least four times in a week; and (5) must be willing to participate and become part of the study. The exclusion criteria are as follows: (1) those considered as non-frequent users who only visited once in the public library and may not be able to utilized the facilities, resources or availed library services; (2) those users who are not professionals; and (3) those users who are not willing to become respondents of the study.

The proposed distribution of respondents in public libraries namely: Public Library A, Public Library B, Public Library C, Public Library D, and Public Library E in region 12. It indicates that in every identified public library, the researcher gathered at least 35 respondents using stratified sampling technique, provided that the respondents who have met the inclusion criteria are willing to answer the survey questionnaire.

Instruments

This study employed two research instruments, namely, (1) an adapted standardized research instrument developed by Emiri and Olise (2022) to measure service quality, and (2) a self-made questionnaire to measure users' library engagement. The first instrument was slightly modified and is composed of 5 indicators with 5 statements per indicator while the second instrument, which is a self-made questionnaire, contains 3 indicators with 7 statements per indicator designed to measure the users' degree of library engagement. It was answered by the respondents using a five-point Likert Scale of 1-5, 1 being the lowest and 5 being the highest.

To determine the content validity and reliability of the two instruments, it was subjected to the following tests: First, the instrument was pilot tested to at least thirty-five (35) respondents who were selected randomly in order to determine the instrument's Cronbach's Alpha and establish its reliability. Second, the content of the instrument was validated by three (3) experts in Library and Information Science. The two adopted and self-made questionnaires were pilot tested to about 35 respondents to test and establish their reliability and internal consistency. Data gathered from the pilot testing were processed and tested using Cronbach's Alpha to establish reliability and internal consistency. Jim, (n.d.) stated that Cronbach's Alpha is a measure used to assess the reliability or internal consistency of a set of scale or test items. In other words, the reliability of any given measurement refers to which it is a consistent measure of a concept, a Cronbach's Alpha is one way of measuring the strength of that consistency. Results of the reliability statistics got a Cronbach Alpha value of (.733) for assurance, empathy (.725), reliability (.719), responsiveness (.708), tangibility (.776), behavioral domain (.708), emotional domain (.761), and cognitive domain (.843). Results of the reliability statistics shows that Cronbach's Alpha were all above 0.70 which implies that all items tested passed the test of reliability and internal consistency.

Finally, the instrument was submitted to three experts of the topic to establish the content validity of the instrument. One expert validator is the program coordinator of Master of Library and Information Science of one of the private higher education institutions in one of the colleges in Digos City. The second validator is a Director of Learning and Resource Center in one of the colleges in Digos City, and the third was a Graduate School Faculty in one of the colleges in Digos City. Results in Table 5 revealed that the overall mean score is 4.50 and interpreted to be as Excellent. This result indicates that the instrument is found to be excellent in terms of its clarity of directions and items, presentation and organization of items, suitability of items, adequateness of items per category indicator, attainment of purpose, objectivity and scale and evaluation rating scale.

Procedure

The study followed a series of processes and procedures to ensure its validity and ethical conduct. Firstly, the researcher obtained an endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School, Cor Jesu College, Inc. to conduct the study. Secondly, an ethical clearance was secured from Cor Jesu College, Inc. Research Ethics Committee. Thirdly, the researcher obtained a letter of approval from the head librarians among public libraries in Region XII, namely Public Library A, Public Library B, Public Library C, Public Library D, and Public Library E, to conduct the study involving 175 library users; Once approved by the public head librarians among public libraries in Region XII, with the help of librarians, the identified respondents were approached by the researcher, and were personally asked to participate in the study; Once consent was given, the researcher personally distributed the survey questionnaires to the respondents; Retrieval of instrument then followed, and all the data gathered were tabulated, processed, and analyzed using the most appropriate statistical tools. Finally, the study results were disseminated through a thesis defense, where the researcher presented and defended the master's thesis in front of a panel of experts, allowing for detailed discussion, presentation of findings, and response to questions. Additionally, the findings were published in relevant academic journals for peer-reviewed publication, contributing to the academic literature and reaching a wider audience of scholars and professionals.

Ethical Considerations

In conducting the survey, the researcher ensured that the respondents voluntarily participated in the study, and that no harm inflicted

to the respondents. The survey questionnaire used in this study did not ask for any personal information from the respondents to ensure the anonymity of the data. In addition, the gathered data were treated with confidentiality.

Data Analysis

To interpret and analyze all the gathered data, the following statistical tools were employed. Mean scores were used to measure the level of service quality and the level of users' engagement in public libraries in Region XII. A group of numbers may be averaged by adding them all up and dividing the result by the total count. This is known as the mean. It stands for the dataset's typical or core value (Lind, Marchal, & Wathen, 2018). Additionally, simple linear regression analysis was also utilized to figure out if one independent variable can influence the dependent variable (Bevans, 2023). In this particular study, the researcher employed this tool to determine if the service quality provided by public libraries influences library user's engagement.

Results

The researchers presented the results of the study in three parts, namely the level of service quality of public libraries in terms of assurance, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, and tangibility; level of user's engagement of public libraries in terms of behavioral domain, emotional domain, and cognitive domain; and the significant influence of service quality of public libraries on the library user's engagement.

Level of Service Quality among Public Libraries in Region XII

Table 1 shows the level of service quality in terms of assurance, empathy, reliability, responsiveness and tangibility. Results reveal that the respondents are extremely satisfied of the service quality provided among public libraries with an overall mean of 4.44. This implies that respondents strongly agree with the statements in all indicators, namely: assurance (4.53), empathy (4.33), reliability (4.46), responsiveness (4.49), and tangibility (4.40). Their means score was not far from each other and among the five indicators of service quality, Assurance was the highest and Empathy has the lowest mean but still the result came out extremely satisfied. Thus, the combination of these five dimensions may increase the level of service quality among public libraries.

Table 1. *Results and Interpretation on the Level of Service Quality in terms of Assurance, Empathy, Reliability, Responsiveness, and Tangibility*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Assurance	4.53	Strongly Agree	It indicates that the respondents are extremely assured that the skills of the librarians are adequate in terms of providing professional support, securing data, and treating users with care and respect.
Empathy	4.33	Strongly Agree	It indicates that the respondents are extremely satisfied that librarians always give attention in caring and professional manner, know and understand users' needs, have the ability to deliver services effectively that makes users feel more valued.
Reliability	4.46	Strongly Agree	It indicates that the respondents are extremely satisfied that librarians provide information services as needed, show sincere interest in solving problems by providing the right services at the right time.
Responsiveness	4.49	Strongly Agree	It indicates that in terms of responsiveness, the respondents are extremely satisfied that librarians always provide library assistance to help library users in information searching and retrieval, provide available library resources and services with immediate responses to patron's request.
Tangibility	4.40	Strongly Agree	It indicates that in terms of tangibility, the respondents are extremely satisfied with adequate library equipment, conducive learning environment, relevant library materials with qualified library staff.
Overall	4.44	Strongly Agree	It indicates that the respondents are extremely satisfied on the level of service quality in terms of assurance, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, and tangibility.

Level of User's Engagement among Public Libraries in Region XII

Table 2. *Results and Interpretation on the Level of Users Engagement among Public Libraries in Region XII in terms of Behavioral, Emotional and Cognitive Domains*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Descriptive Rating</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Behavioral Domain	4.31	Strongly Agree	It indicates that in behavioral domain, the respondents are extremely engaged in terms of preference to study, read, and search, utilization of reference books, using Web OPAC and computers, and seeking assistance from the librarians.
Emotional Domain	4.40	Strongly Agree	It indicates that in emotional domain, the respondents are extremely engaged and feel interested and comfortable doing research work, with photocopying and printing services, good ambiance, and ease of using the resources.
Cognitive Domain	4.48	Strongly Agree	It indicates that in cognitive domain, the respondents are extremely engaged to meet informational needs, improve reading comprehension and vocabulary, enhance knowledge and understanding, solve practical research problems, and

			strengthen their ability to retrieve reliable information.
Overall	4.40	Strongly Agree	It indicates that the level of user’s engagement in terms of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive domains are extremely engaged.

Table 2 shows the level of user’s engagement in terms of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive. It was observed that the respondents are extremely engaged with the library with an overall mean of 4.40. This indicates that the respondents were very agreeable with the three indicators, namely: behavioral domain (4.31), emotional domain (4.40), and cognitive domain (4.48). Their means score was not far from each other and among the three indicators of user’s engagement, the cognitive domain was found out with a highest mean while the behavioral domain has the lowest mean but still the result was extremely engaged. Thus, the presence of these three indicators may increase the level of library user’s engagement of the respondents.

Influence of Service Quality on the Library User’s Engagement

Table 3 presents the significant influence of service quality of public libraries on the library user’s engagement with their corresponding regression and beta coefficient values.

Table 3. Results and Interpretation on the Influence of Service Quality Towards Library Users’ Engagement among Public Libraries in Region XII

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig
(Constant)	.851	.216		3.942	.000
Service Quality	.798	.048	.782	16.490	.000

Adjusted R Square = .609; Sig = .000; Df = 173; F Statistic = 271.911

Table 3 shows that when regression equation UE (Users’ Engagement) = β₀ + β₁SQ (Service Quality) + ε_i is tested using Simple Linear Regression Analysis, results from the ANOVA table show that the sig-value is .000 which is found to be below the .05 level of significance set for this study (see Appendix I). This implies that overall, the model is considered to be significant and that the model fits the data.

When looking at the regression coefficient of SQ (Service Quality), the estimated regression model can be mathematically presented as:

$$UE = .851 (\text{constant}) + .798 (SQ) + \epsilon_i$$

The value of the beta coefficient for SQ (Service Quality) implies that holding all other variables in the regression constant, its coefficient indicates that for every one (1) unit change in the level of SQ (Service Quality) would give a corresponding .798 unit increase in the level of UE (Users’ Engagement). This implies that as the level of service quality of public libraries increases, the level of users’ engagement of public libraries also increases. Thus, it can be claimed that one effective way of enticing more individuals to use public libraries is to improve the level of service quality of public libraries. The high positive beta coefficient with p-value of .000 for Service Quality confirms the empirical findings which claimed that Service Quality can significantly predict Users Engagement. Perceptions of high service quality also lead to high customer satisfaction and user engagement (Giovanis et al., 2016). Through this specific type of user engagement tools, libraries can improve their services and provide high-quality services to their users, thus service quality aspects influence library user engagement (Quach et al., 2016). Therefore, Partap (2019) concluded that service quality is the extent to which users are provided with good resources and library services to achieve a higher level of user engagement.

In its entirety, the explanatory and predictive power of Service Quality is considered to be high because it could account about 60.90 percent of the variation in the Users’ Engagement. This is manifested in the model summary table which shows that the value of the Adjusted R Square is .609 which implies that about 60.90 percent of the variations in the Service Quality can be explained by the variations in the User’s Engagement. The remaining 39.10 percent unexplained variation could be accounted for by other variables not included in the model.

Discussion

Investigating the influence of service quality of public libraries on the library user’s engagement could be essential for public library administrators, public library association, public librarians, local government unit (LGU), community and future researchers. The results of the study could increase their awareness vis-à-vis these variables.

Level of Service Quality among Public Libraries in Region XII

This indicates that service quality in terms of assurance, the respondents are extremely satisfied and assured that the skills of the librarians are adequate in terms of providing security of data, professional assistance to research works, treating library users with care and respect and librarians have confidence and expertise in answering users’ queries. These findings were validated by some authors. According to Setonio and Hidayat (2022), assurance relates to the knowledge and courtesy of library staff and their ability to generate trust and confidence and make users’ feel safe when conducting transactions. Also, Emiri and Olise (2022) emphasized that library

personnel instill trust and confidence in providing quality services through their knowledge, expertise and skills to improve library services for patrons. Similarly, Tabuyo et al. (2019) stated that providing service quality in terms of assurance, the library staff have the confidence on responding to the concerns and queries of the library users. Additionally, Gam (2020) pointed that service quality with assurance improves satisfaction of the library users.

Further, indicates that service quality in terms of empathy indicates that respondents are extremely satisfied with the librarians' attention and care before, during, and after library use. Librarians understand and address users' needs professionally, making them feel valued and special. Amanullah, Hazan, and Hafez (2021) confirm that users appreciate a caring attitude from librarians. Tabuyo et al. (2019) note that empathy is shown when librarians eagerly meet users' needs. Kartanegara and Keni (2021) state that understanding users' needs enhances satisfaction. Setonio and Hidayat (2022) emphasize that empathy involves individual attention, care, and prioritizing customer interests. Nur and Fritantus (2021) add that empathy is crucial for understanding community needs, building relationships, and effective communication.

Therefore, the high descriptive rating for service quality indicates that respondents are extremely satisfied with public libraries in terms of assurance, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, and tangibility. Setiono and Hidayat (2022) concluded that continuous improvement of these dimensions enhances user satisfaction. Fida et al. (2020) highlighted the importance of these five dimensions: reliability, providing services as promised and correctly the first time; responsiveness, the willingness to help and provide quick service; assurance, generating trust and confidence, making users feel safe; empathy, giving personal attention and understanding users' needs; and tangibility, having visually appealing facilities, equipment, and professional staff. These aspects collectively ensure a high level of user satisfaction.

Level of User's Engagement among Public Libraries in Region XII

This indicates that the level of users' engagement in terms of cognitive domain is extremely engaged. The respondents believe that the library meets their informational needs, enhances reading comprehension and vocabulary, and aids in understanding difficult topics. Library resources help solve research problems and improve focus and information retrieval. Goulding (2016) asserts that library services should be tailored to meet users' needs for maximum engagement. Quality resources aid decision-making and problem-solving (Bokoh et al., 2023) and increase engagement (Ekeng & Esin, 2021). Anmol et al. (2021) and Di Gangi (2016) confirm that libraries with high-quality resources achieve higher user engagement and usage. Ahmad et al. (2022) note that quality resources attract more patrons and enhance engagement.

Among the three indicators of user engagement, the behavioral domain had the lowest mean, rated as "Strongly Agree." This suggests that respondents were highly engaged with the library, preferring a quiet, convenient study environment with current, relevant reference books, easy-to-navigate web OPAC, and safe, secure computers. They favored staying in the library due to its conducive, visually appealing facilities and sought librarian assistance for research. This preference aligns with findings by Reddy (2017), who emphasized the importance of functional, noise-free environments and adequate lighting. Additionally, Bashir, Soroya, and Khanum (2016) and Michnik (2015) highlighted that current collections and well-maintained facilities enhance library engagement.

Therefore, as to the level of user's engagement the result found out that it is in the high descriptive rating, which means that the respondents are extremely engaged on the level of user's engagement of public libraries in terms of behavioral, emotional, and cognitive domains. This result was supported by some authors. For example, Peacemaker and Heinze (2015) observed that libraries with updated resources, adequate facilities and available services emotionally inspire users to engage more in libraries. Additionally, user engagement with emotional factors influences librarians to understand and create deeper relationship with library users (Zhao, Cao & Yang, 2020). Furthermore, Khosravi, Behzadi and Nowkarizi (2024) stated that the higher level of cognitive experience, acquiring knowledge and computer skills and use of library's OPAC in libraries have influenced on the increased of user engagement.

Influence of Service Quality on the Library User's Engagement

The study revealed a significant influence of service quality on the library user's engagement. Results indicate that the high positive beta coefficient with p-value of .000 for Service Quality confirms the empirical findings which claimed that Service Quality can significantly predict Users Engagement. This implies that as the level of service quality of public libraries increases, the level of users' engagement of public libraries also increases. Perceptions of high service quality also lead to high customer satisfaction and user engagement (Giovanis et al., 2016). Through this specific type of user engagement tools, libraries can improve their services and provide high-quality services to their users, thus service quality aspects influence library user engagement (Quach et al., 2016). Therefore, Partap (2019) concluded that service quality is the extent to which users are provided with good resources and library services to achieve a higher level of user engagement.

In its entirety, the explanatory and predictive power of Service Quality is considered to be high because it could account about 60.90 percent of the variation in the Users' Engagement. This is manifested in the model summary table which shows that the value of the Adjusted R Square is .609 which implies that about 60.90 percent of the variations in the Service Quality can be explained by the variations in the User's Engagement. The remaining 39.10 percent unexplained variation could be accounted for by other variables not included in the model.

Furthermore, libraries that provide high-quality services typically demonstrate high levels of user engagement. Quality services in public libraries significantly impact user engagement (Biranvand, Ghaffari & Haghirosadat, 2019). Taufiq et al. (2020) found a positive relationship between high-quality services and user satisfaction and engagement. Effective, informative, and accessible services encourage library engagement (Corpuz, 2020). Libraries offering quality services are more likely to be patronized and positively influence user engagement (Ahmad, Saleh & AbdulRazaq, 2022).

Libraries that provide users with what they want achieve higher levels of user engagement (Anmol, Khan & Muhammad, 2021). Public libraries with high-quality resources are more likely to be patronized, positively impacting perceived quality and user engagement (Ahmad, Saleh & Abdulrazaq, 2022). The availability and adequacy of relevant resources significantly affect user engagement. Wanyonyi et al. (2018) found a positive impact of resource quality on user engagement, emphasizing the importance of qualified, knowledgeable, and skilled library staff. Competent staff delivering effective services enhance user engagement (Young & Kelly, 2019). Alam (2020) also noted that the tangibility of library facilities significantly affects user satisfaction and engagement.

Therefore, service quality significantly influences user engagement and satisfaction. Twum et al. (2020) showed that all service quality dimensions positively impact library user satisfaction. Ahmed (2017) highlighted that assurance, empathy, reliability, and responsiveness significantly affect library services and user satisfaction. In the UAE, public libraries developed innovative ways to provide quality services, ensuring access to information, adequate collections, and engaging programs (Zimba, Mavodza & Eid, 2015). In Zambia, city libraries demonstrated high user engagement and satisfaction with library access, facilities, and service quality (Nzazi, 2018). Moses et al. (2016) also revealed that service quality significantly influences library user engagement and satisfaction.

Conclusion

Service quality in public libraries is a critical factor in determining the level of user engagement. The dimensions of service quality, including assurance, empathy, reliability, responsiveness, and tangibility, each dimension play a significant role in shaping user experiences and engagement across behavioral, emotional, and cognitive domains. Here's a deeper insight into how service quality impacts library user engagement: assurance, refers to the knowledge and courtesy of library staff and their ability to convey trust and confidence; empathy, involves the caring and personalized attention the library provides to its users; reliability, is the ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately; responsiveness, is the willingness to help users and provide prompt service; and tangibility, includes the physical facilities, equipment, and appearance of personnel. Therefore, high service quality leads satisfied users to engaged more frequent library visits, participate in library programs and events, recommend the library to others, users develop positive feelings towards the library, fostering loyalty and advocacy, enhanced learning and knowledge for their cognitive growth and support users' learning and research needs.

To enhance service quality and user engagement, libraries should have regular staff training, actively seeking users feedback, integrating modern technology, engaging with community, and improving library facilities. By focusing on these dimensions, public libraries can poster a positive, engaging, and supportive environment that significantly increased user engagement and satisfaction leading to a more vibrant and active library community.

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